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Main author: **Tjalf de Boer (MLS)**

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Executive Summary

PFAS in the environment are known as “forever chemicals” as they are not easily broken down by physical or biological processes. To prevent PFAS from entering the environment, it should be broken down at the sources, such as wastewater treatment facilities. Here we investigate two different biological degradation methods that could be incorporated in wider PFAS treatment trains to remove PFAS during the wastewater treatment process. Both fungal and bacterial degradation were tested using white rot fungal enzymes (laccase mediator system) and a community of *Pseudomonas* bacteria. Degradation times were kept within a practical range (up to 6 weeks), and degradation efficiency was determined using an effect-based bioassay. Laccase-mediator degradation of both PFOA and PFOS remained inconclusive, in which initially there was less signal in the bioassay up till week 4, but this increased again in weeks 5 and 6. For the bacterial degradation using a *Pseudomonas* community, robust degradation of PFAS-containing firefighting foam was observed in two independent experiments where approximately 80% of the PFAS signal disappeared after 6 weeks. Bacterial degradation showed a better degradation profile than using fungal enzymes, which may be caused by the constant renewal of degradation enzymes produced by the growing bacteria. For the fungal degradation experiments, enzymes were only renewed once a week. Weekly renewal may mean that degradation takes longer and beyond the incubation times used in this study.

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1 Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and other Persistent Mobile Toxicants (PMT) are persistent environmental contaminants due to their strong atomic bonds, such as the carbon-fluorine (C–F) bond, making them resistant to conventional degradation methods ¹. Current chemical or physical methods for PFAS degradation require harsh chemicals or high temperatures, which can make them environmentally unfriendly or economically unfeasible. Biological degradation using microorganisms or enzymes derived thereof may form an alternative for chemical/physical PFAS degradation. Among emerging bioremediation strategies, laccase enzymes, also known as multi-copper oxidases, are known for oxidizing a broad range of organic compounds and have shown potential in PFAS degradation, particularly when used with mediators or synergistic treatment approaches ². Laccases catalyze the oxidation of phenolic and aromatic substrates, generating radical intermediates that can facilitate further degradation processes. Although laccases alone have limited efficacy in breaking the stable C–F bonds in PFAS, studies suggest that laccase-mediator systems or combined enzymatic treatments may enhance defluorination ³. Laccase mediators are small molecules that can be oxidized by laccase into reactive intermediates, which can subsequently react with molecules that are not necessarily laccase substrates, such as PFAS or polymers such as plastics ⁴. One of the properties of the laccase mediator system is that through the mediator, laccases are often able to oxidize compounds with a high redox potential ⁵. This potentially makes them good enzymes to defluorinate PFAS molecules.

Previously we showed that laccases from the white rot fungus *Rigidoporus sp. FMD21* are able to degrade 2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin (TCDD) one of the most potent and toxic dioxins ⁶. As FMD21 is a high laccase producing fungal strain, the goal of this study was to investigate if FMD21 laccases can degrade PFAS in the presence of mediator molecules such as 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (HBT) and 2,2'-azino-bis(3ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonicacid (TEMPO). Laccase mediators are molecules that resemble natural laccase substrates, which are oxidized into radicals. As radicals they can oxidize non laccase substrates and extend the range of molecules oxidized by laccases ⁷. An alternative to fungal enzymes for biodegradation of PFAS is the use of bacteria. It has been shown that certain bacterial species can degrade PFAS and other fluorinated compounds. Several strains of *Pseudomonas* bacteria are known to aerobically degrade PFAS. For example, *P. aeruginosa* and *P.*

putida were able to biotransform between 20% and 27% of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and 47% of perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) in 96 hours ⁸.

The PROMISCES project (<https://promisces.eu/>) seeks to find novel and innovative technologies for PFAS and other Persistent Mobile Toxicants (PMTs) remediation from environmental matrices such as soil, sediment, and surface and wastewater. Biological treatment of PFAS could be a valuable addition to these technologies. One of the technologies aimed to be developed during the project is biological PFAS degradation by the use of laccase enzymes from white-rot fungi. In this study we compare two different biological degradation methods for PFAS degradation: enzymatic degradation by the laccase mediator system and bacterial degradation using a community of different *Pseudomonas* strains. A community of bacteria was used rather than individual strains due to the potential synergistic enzymatic activity of the different strains ⁹. We focused on PFOA and PFOS for degradation due to their environmental relevance ¹⁰ and a firefighting foam (AFFF) that contained a mix of PFAS compounds (see SI table 1 for information on the AFFF composition). Degradation experiments lasted up to 6 weeks, after which the remaining PFAS was measured to determine degradation rates.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 TTR-T4 FITC PFAS bioassay

PFAS residues were measured using the effect-based TTR-T4 FITC bioassay ¹¹. Briefly, prior to using the bioassay, FITC-T4 was produced in-house by incubating T4 (Merck, Burlington, MA, USA) and FITC (Merck) together for 1 hour at 37°C, after which the conjugated FITC-T4 molecule was purified using NH₄-Acetate precipitation and subsequent Sephadex purification. The TTR-T4 FITC was performed in 96-well plates (Greiner, Kremsmünster, Austria) using Tris buffer, TTR protein (30 nM) and FITC-T4 (100 nM) and either the sample or a reference. The plates were incubated at room temperature, after which the fluorescence was measured using a Mithras LB40 plate reader (Berthold, Bad Wildbad, Germany).

2.2 Enzymatic fungal degradation

We showed previously that *Rigidoporus* strain FMD21 produces high amounts of extracellular laccase, which can be isolated directly from the growth medium ¹². To produce laccase enzymes, fungal hyphae were transferred from culture plates to PDSRb medium and grown to high density

(approximately 3-4 days), after which the growth medium was separated from the fungal biomass by centrifugation and filtration. Collected laccase enzymes were purified using ion exchange chromatography (HiTrap IEX anion exchange column on an AKTA Pure system (Cytiva, Marlborough, USA). Laccase activity was determined using the ABTS assay¹³ as described previously. Degradation studies consisted of adding 200 units/ml of laccase, mediator (HBT or TEMPO) at 5 μ M and PFAS (PFOA or PFOS) (1 μ M) to citrate buffer (25 mM, pH 4.5), after which they were incubated at 30 °C for up to 6 weeks. Fresh laccase enzyme was added weekly during incubation. After incubation the PFAS was extracted using wax-based solid phase extraction (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) and measured using the TTR-T4 FITC bioassay. Incubations on the AFFF used a different concentration of AFFF (5 mg/L) as compared to PFOA/PFOS due to a lower solubility.

2.3 Bacterial degradation

A community of 8 different *Pseudomonas* strains was created (see SI table 2 for strain information). Each strain was grown from an in-house glycerol stock individually in medium for 16 hours, after which the density was measured (OD₆₀₀) and the bacteria were collected by centrifugation. The community was created by adding the different strains in equal density together in nutrient broth medium, after which glycerol stocks of 0.5 mL were created for use in degradation experiments. Bacterial degradation was only performed on the AFFF. Degradation was performed in 100 mL flasks using 30 mL of M9 medium with the addition of yeast extract (0.1%) and AFFF (mg/L). Flasks were incubated with 0.5 mL of *Pseudomonas* community glycerol stock and incubated on a shaker at 150 RPM and 30 °C for up to 6 weeks.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Enzymatic fungal degradation

Enzymatic degradation using fungal laccase enzymes was performed on PFOA, PFOS, and a mix of PFAS contained in AFFF. The proposed mechanism for PFAS degradation using the laccase mediator system is via a combination of free radical decarboxylation, rearrangement, and coupling processes, which results in defluorination¹⁴. The addition of mediators seems to be essential for PFAS degradation by laccase enzymes. For this reason, two different laccase mediators (HBT and TEMPO) were tested. In theory the laccase mediators are oxidized by the laccase to form radicals which in

turn can oxidize other molecules such as PFAS. By using mediators as intermediate radicals, compounds that do not fit into the laccase active site can also be oxidized.

HBT was chosen as it is a classic laccase mediator and TEMPO because of its potential to form a potent radical that easily reacts with other molecules¹⁵. For the incubation with PFOA, three conditions (laccase, laccase + TEMPO and laccase + HBT) were compared to a negative control (no enzyme or mediator). Both laccase and mediators were added fresh each week. PFOA concentration for each week was measured using a TTR/T4-FITC binding bioassay. Results of this experiment are shown in Figure 1, which shows the relative PFOA equivalents per week as compared to the negative control. The results showed that from week 3 onwards, large differences were observed between conditions which included conditions that seemingly seemed to increase in PFOA equivalents when laccase was added. Overall, the results remained inconclusive, as for some conditions the PFOA equivalent concentration seemed to go down at first but then went up at the end of the experiment, where week 6 showed higher TTR-T4 FITC bioactivity for all three enzyme conditions as compared to the control.

Figure 1, Fungal enzymatic degradation of PFOA measured in weeks 1–6. The negative control (no enzymes added) is set at 100% and other conditions are set at the percentage PFOA equivalent of the negative control.

A repeat of the experiment, which also included PFOS next to PFOA was performed with a difference in setup where only the laccase was added each week but the mediators were only added at the start.

Figure 2, Fungal enzymatic degradation of PFOA (left) and PFOS (right) measured in weeks 3 – 6. The negative control (no enzymes added) is set at 100% and other conditions are set at the percentage PFOA equivalent of the negative control.

The reasoning for this is that mediators are not consumed in the reaction, and a buildup of mediators in the reaction may inhibit enzyme activity when high concentrations are reached. Incubations were run for another 6 weeks, but this time remaining PFAS was only measured at week 6. For both types of PFAS (PFOA and PFOS) no degradation was observed after 6 weeks of incubation (Figure 2 as compared to the negative control). A single addition of mediators at the start did not seem to have a positive effect on laccase-mediated PFAS degradation. PFAS degradation experiments using the laccase mediator system for the white-rot fungus *Rigidoporus FMD21* were repeated multiple times but the results to show if laccase enzymes from this fungus, with the addition of two different mediators, can degrade polyfluorinated compounds remain inconclusive. While there is the possibility that laccases from this fungus simply do not degrade PFAS-like compounds, there were some unknowns that could not be answered by the experiments. First, the incubation time used here was 6 weeks, while similar degradation experiments in literature use a longer incubation time (up to 6 months) 16. The reason 6 weeks were used instead of longer incubation times was practicality. For the use of wastewater treatment, a long turnover time of the water treatment would mean that extra steps like concentrating the water or filtering would be needed. However, 6 weeks may not be a long enough incubation time for a significant percentage of the PFAS to be enzymatically broken down. Another uncertainty is the use of the effect-based bioassay. The TTR-T4 FITC bioassay is responsive to many polyfluorinated compounds (albeit with different potencies), which normally is considered

a strength, as a single measurement of an environmental sample would capture activities otherwise not measured with chemical analysis on a fixed set of PFAS. However, when measuring degradation of a parent compound, it may not be able to detect breakdown if the potency of the transformation products has an equal potency. This may also explain the large differences seen each week in the initial PFOA breakdown experiment where degradation was measured weekly.

3.2 Bacterial degradation

An alternative for biological PFAS degradation to using fungal laccase enzymes may be the use of bacteria. Bacteria have the benefit of not having to be produced separately, as they can rapidly grow at the initial stages of the incubation. Pseudomonas bacteria are known for their wide variety of metabolic activities, which can include degradation of xenobiotic compounds. Several mechanisms have been proposed for the microbial degradation of PFAS. It has been shown that certain strains of Pseudomonas can degrade PFAS both aerobically and anaerobically, for which aerobic degradation is preferable to anaerobic degradation due to its practicality¹⁷. For the sulfonic acids such as PFOS,

Figure 3, bacterial degradation of PFAS in AFFF using a pseudomonas community in two separate experiments (R1 and R2). Negative controls (NC) and blanks are averaged between the two experiments, and the NC is set at 100%. +Y means yeast extract was added at the start of the incubation.

desulfonation by Pseudomonas bacteria was observed previously¹⁸. Removing the sulfonic group leaves the rest of the molecule open to nuclear attack and further defluorination¹⁹ and ultimately degradation. Perfluorinated carboxylic acids like PFOA are directly defluorinated by pseudomonas²⁰.

We created a synthetic community of 8 different *Pseudomonas* strains to test if this community would be able to degrade a mix of different PFAS contained in a firefighting foam (AFFF). The choice was made for a community as it is more flexible to use in different real-life scenarios (a single strain may not perform well in different conditions), and different strains may synergistically enhance breakdown if multiple types of enzymes are involved²¹. The bacterial community was incubated for 6 weeks with AFFF in minimal medium with and without the addition of yeast extract as an external nutrient source. Compared to the negative control (no bacteria added). All conditions showed considerable degradation of the PFAS from the AFFF (Figure 3). To exclude that PFAS did not accumulate in the bacterial biomass this was measured separately but did not show activity (results not shown). Bacterial community degradation of AFFF showed degradation percentages of approximately 80% in both separate experiments. As blank (no AFFF added) values were also around 15% of the negative control (no bacteria added), degradation may have been higher but could not be measured due to background activity. When the experiment was repeated, similar breakdown percentages were reached. Although some bacterial growth was observed in the negative control because the AFFF could not be sterilized, no breakdown was observed.

4 Conclusion

Two different methods of biological degradation of PFAS were studied with the goal of investigating their application in the water treatment cycle. Fungal laccase enzyme did not show significant degradation within 6 weeks when incubates were measured with an effect-based bioassay. Bacterial degradation using a community of different *Pseudomonas* strains did achieve considerable PFAS degradation in AFFF after 4 weeks. While the two technologies are too different to be compared directly, we propose that the bacteria may produce a range of different enzymes and that their presence during the incubation means they can constantly replenish these enzymes, which may facilitate faster breakdown than when a single enzyme is used that is only added once a week. Future experiments may include identifying transformation products for both degradation techniques and determining if toxicity is actually reduced, as transformation products may have a comparable biological activity as the parent compounds.

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6 Supportive information

6.1 SI Table 1

PFAS concentrations in the fire-fighting foam (AFFF) used in the bacterial degradation experiment.

abbr. name	name	Concentration (mg/L)
PFBA	Perfluorobutyric acid	0.4
PFPeA	Perfluoropentanoic acid	0.3
PFHxA	Perfluorohexanoic acid	7
PFHpA	Perfluoroheptanoic acid	0.1
PFOA	perfluorooctanoic acid	0.05
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid	0.003
PFDA	Perfluorodecanoic acid	0.025
PFUnDA	Perfluoroundecanoic acid	0.002
PFDODA	Perfluorododecanoic acid	0.01
PFTeDA	Perfluorotetradecanoic acid	0.005
4:2 FTSA	4:2 Fluorotelomer Sulfonic acid	1.5
6:2 FTSA	6:2 Fluorotelomer Sulfonic acid	400
8:2 FTSA	8:2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acids	2
10:2 FTSA	10:2 Fluorotelomer Sulfonic acid	1
5:3 FTCA	5:3 Fluorotelomer carboxylic acid	0.005

6.2 SI Table 2

Information on each of the strains added to the bacterial degradation community

Isolate	Strain	Origin
SSE-5C_1	<i>Pseudomonas fildesensis</i>	PLA enrichment
SSE-2A	<i>Pseudomonas kilonensis</i>	PLA enrichment
SSE-5A_2	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	PLA enrichment
L-3w2	<i>Pseudomonas lini</i>	LLDPE enrichment
RL-8	<i>Pseudomonas defluvii</i>	PFOS RWS soil enrichment
PF-5	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> PF-5 B-23831 ARS (<i>Pseudomonas protegens</i>)	ATCC
Phz24	<i>Pseudomonas chlororaphis</i> Phz24	ATCC
SH-C52	<i>Pseudomonas corrugata</i> SH-C52 WT (<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>)	gift WUR
DC300	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> DC3000	ATCC
B1	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> (B1)	gift WUR
D1	<i>Pseudomonas</i> (D1)	gift WUR
C11	<i>Pseudomonas</i> (C11)	gift WUR

